

THE EFFECT OF COVID PANDEMIC ON CRYPTOCURRENCY MARKETS: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The consequences of Covid-19 on the financial sector have gained so much attention. At the same time, another growing part of the financial markets is cryptocurrencies, and it comes to the question: What is the impact of Covid-19 as a shock on crypto markets? This study is the first attempt to survey the growing literature on the relationship between the Covid outbreak and crypto markets. I first review research on the implications of Covid on the crypto market in a general setting. Then I examine research on herding behavior during Covid in the crypto market and the efficiency and volatility of cryptocurrencies during the same period. I conclude by discussing the crypto market's relationship with other financial assets during Covid.

JEL: G10, G12, G15

KEYWORDS: Covid-19, Cryptocurrency, Bitcoin, Herding Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

With the downfall of the global financial system during the 2008 financial crisis, cryptocurrencies or digital currencies have emerged as a new class of assets. Cryptocurrencies have drawn much interest from investors and governments due to their novelty. Also, research on cryptocurrency has seen an enormous rise, with exponential growth, in recent years. The novel coronavirus disease, also known as Covid-19, further caught the interest of experts as financial market variables reacted badly to the announcement of the pandemic made by the World Health Organization in 2020. During the Covid-19 pandemic, several studies have been conducted to determine whether cryptocurrencies are safe havens or diversifiers. These studies sometimes compare cryptocurrencies with traditional assets, like gold and stocks.

The characteristics of cryptocurrencies created the opportunity for the need for such studies. Cryptocurrencies are decentralized and not controlled by any government or central bank, resulting in a disconnection between them and the actual economy. Some studies have been conducted, and they have arrived at contradictory findings. Depending on the study, cryptocurrencies may or may not be safe havens. This contradiction may arise because researchers have focused on various regions and used various research methods. In general, the type of studies that have been made in the area of cryptocurrencies and the Covid pandemic can be divided into five categories: general aspect of the crypto market during covid, herding behavior during covid in the crypto market, impact of covid on crypto efficiency and returns, the volatility of crypto markets during covid and relationship with other financial assets during covid.

The organization of this paper is as follows. The first section will briefly explain my methodology for this literature review. In the following section, I review five categories of papers related to the relationship between Covid and the crypto market. First, I start with the research on the general relationship between the crypto market and covid outbreak. In this part, some studies use covid as a structural break and examine the cryptocurrency market before and during the covid. The second part of this section is about the herding behavior of traders. Because of the nature of covid, analyzing the herding effect in the crypto market has gained lots of attention.

Moreover, the return of cryptocurrencies and their volatility of them also made a considerable part of the literature in the past two years. After that, I will go through the efficiency of crypto assets and the volatility of the crypto market during the Covid crisis. Finally, I review papers showing the connection between cryptocurrencies and other asset classes during the covid era to understand crypto assets in the financial sector better. In the final part, I briefly discuss how crypto markets and their participants could behave in the post-Covid era.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This survey is based on studies that mainly addressed the intersection of crypto markets and the Covid pandemic and is based on a keyword-based systematic literature review. Following the strategy proposed by Petticrew and Roberts (2008) and employed by Zarifhonarvar (2023), I excluded publications that did not directly connect to the relationship between the Covid crisis and crypto markets after gathering 200 papers based on their keyword usage at Google Scholar. After that, I divided the papers into five categories depending on their topics. This literature review contains studies published between February 2019 and January 2023.

LITERATURE REVIEW

GENERAL ASPECTS OF CRYPTO MARKETS DURING COVID

One of the early research that explores the connections between the leading cryptocurrencies in the cryptocurrency markets in cases with and without the Covid-19 pandemic is Aysan, Khan, and Topuz (2021). The nine cryptocurrencies that have been selected in this paper are Bitcoin, Ethereum, Ripple, Litecoin, Eos, BitcoinCash, Binance, Stellar, and Tron. They use daily closing price data for these cryptocurrencies from coinmarketcap for the time period between September 13, 2017, and September 21, 2020. They show that regardless of whether a pandemic is currently underway or not, there is compelling evidence of a long-term connection between Bitcoin and other altcoins. They imply that when investors establish investment plans and strategies, they consider Bitcoin and altcoins together as they provide sustainability and robustness over the long term against different risks and even in the difficult time of the Covid-19 outbreak.

In the same vein, Katsiampa, Yarovaya, and Zięba (2022) uses high-frequency data from January 2019 to December 2020 to analyze co-movements and correlations between Bitcoin and 31 of the most trading crypto assets. They use the data from the pre-Covid and Covid-19 periods to apply the Diagonal-BEKK model, and they find significant changes in patterns of co-movements and correlations during the pandemic period. Additionally, they use the Planar Maximally Filtered Graph (PMFG) and Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) methodologies to analyze how the structure of the crypto asset network changed in response to Covid-19. They show that while it has been established that Bitcoin plays a significant role in the ecosystem of crypto assets, investors are now more interested in crypto assets that fall under the umbrella of dApps (Decentralized Application) and protocols than pure cryptocurrencies.

To show the direct effect of Covid, Demir et al. (2020) investigates the connection between Covid-19 infections and deaths and cryptocurrencies, specifically Bitcoin (BTC), Ethereum (ETH), and Ripple (XRP). This will make it easier to investigate whether cryptocurrencies can protect users against Covid-19 shocks. According to their wavelet coherence analysis, they show that there is initially a negative correlation between the number of reported cases and deaths and Bitcoin, but over time, the correlation turns positive. The results for Ethereum and Ripple are comparable, although the interactions are weaker. They conclude that this result affirms the ability of cryptocurrencies to mitigate the risk posed by Covid-19.

Another recent paper Hong and Yoon (2022) uses network analysis to determine how the cryptocurrency

market has changed due to the Covid-19 outbreak. To do this, they looked at the market's complexity from various angles. To build a cryptocurrency network, they apply a mutual information approach and a correlation coefficient method to compare the daily log return values of 102 digital currencies from January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2020. They build networks based on these two techniques using the planar maximally filtered graph and the least spanning tree. In both time frames, cryptocurrency pairs with significant mutual information are more recognizable at higher correlation coefficient levels than low or zero correlation coefficient values.

They also review the topological and statistical characteristics of these networks. The degree distribution is shown to follow a power-law in numerical data, and the network measurements in the graphs after the Covid-19 outbreak differ noticeably from those before. Additionally, the topological, statistical, and network behavior characteristics of the graphs produced by each approach differ. In particular, it can be observed that Ethereum and Qtum are the most significant cryptocurrencies in both techniques during the post-Covid-19 timeframe. Their findings give investors insight and expectations for disseminating cryptocurrency knowledge in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic's unpredictability.

HERDING BEHAVIOR DURING COVID IN THE CRYPTO MARKET

One of the most exciting topics in the financial sector is the herding behavior of agents. Investors who exhibit herding behavior copy other people's stock selections without considering the fundamentals. In other words, herding occurs in finance when investors disregard their own analysis and follow the herd. This phenomenon has many implications in the crypto market due to the nature of cryptocurrencies and their investors.

To see this effect in the crypto market during the Covid outbreak, Guzmán, Pinto-Gutiérrez, and Trujillo (2021) investigates how Covid-19 lockdowns affect the volume of Bitcoin trading. They discovered that investors became active participants during the Covid-19 outbreak and traded more bitcoins on days with limited mobility related with lockdown mandates using data from Apple mobility trends and different time-series econometric models. They explain by saying that their findings imply that when individual investors have enough free time, they engage in cryptocurrency trading as a hobby and enjoy watching the Bitcoin market. Furthermore, their findings have significant consequences for investor herding behavior, overconfidence, and noisy trading hazards, which can result in bubbles and high trading volume in cryptocurrency markets.

Similarly, Rubbaniy et al. (2021) uses 101 cryptocurrencies from January 2015 to June 2020 to see the herding behavior among crypto traders. Their findings demonstrate that herding behavior exists in crypto markets for the whole sample, and it occurs during both bullish and bearish trends, and crypto investors appear to copy other traders' trading decisions during the Covid-19 pandemic. However, this result seems to be valid only after the lockdowns are relaxed. Their findings do not support the theory that there was any evidence of herding during market lockdowns, which the claim might explain that the lockdowns reduced investor fear and helped them regain trust.

Another early research in this area Susana, Kavisanmathi, and Sreejith (2020) uses the Cross-Sectional Standard Deviation (CSSD) approach to investigate the herding behavior in the cryptocurrency market during the pre-Covid 19 and Covid 19 pandemic periods. This study shows that herding was present among all ten crypto-currencies during the sample period's normal market circumstances but not during market upswings or downswings. However, during the Covid-19 outbreak period, herding behavior was evident in all market situations in Litecoin, Cardano, and Dash.

Finally, an opposite view is Yarovaya, Matkovskyy, and Jalan (2021) that examines cryptocurrency market herding behavior during the Covid-19 outbreak using a variety of quantitative approaches to calculating the

hourly prices of the four most actively traded cryptocurrency markets (USD, EUR, JPY, and KRW) for the period from January 1, 2019, to March 13, 2020. Their findings imply that Covid-19 does not intensify herding in cryptocurrency markets, even though there are very compelling theoretical arguments for observing it in the cryptocurrency market. They show that herding does not become stronger during Covid-19 in any analyzed markets, regardless of whether the market is up or down that day.

IMPACT OF COVID ON CRYPTO EFFICIENCY AND RETURNS

It goes without saying that the essential part of every asset in the financial market is its return. Because of that, the most significant part of the research in the area of Covid and the crypto market belongs to this topic.

To investigate the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on the return of cryptocurrencies Iqbal et al. (2021) examines how the daily addition of new infections around the world represents the changing Covid-19 intensity, impacts the daily returns of the top 10 cryptocurrencies by market capitalization. The Quantile-on-Quantile Regression (QQR) approach's findings show that Covid-19's fluctuating intensity levels have varied effects on the bearish and bullish market scenarios for cryptocurrencies (asymmetric impact). With the exception of Bitcoin, ADA, CRO, and to some extent, Ethereum, most currencies were able to withstand the little Covid-19 shocks by posting profits, but they were unable to withstand the significant waves.

Also, Sahoo (2021) shows the existence of a single, direct causal link between Covid-19 confirmed and fatality cases and cryptocurrency price returns. The post-break period result shows the presence of unidirectional linear causality from Covid-19 confirmed instances to Bitcoin and Ethereum price returns when looking at the break periods. This demonstrates how knowing about the Covid-19 pandemic's progress in advance aids in forecasting when cryptocurrency will reappear.

Likewise, Usman and Nduka (2022) examines the efficiency of cryptocurrencies before and after the period in which Covid-19 was declared a pandemic. They do so by employing a method known as fractional integration. They show that there is consistent evidence of long-term memory across all of the subsamples. In addition, they discovered that the level of Covid-19 persistence was much higher during the pandemic era compared to the period before the pandemic.

Also, according to empirical findings from the generalized Hurst exponent GHE calculation Mnif and Jarboui (2021) shows that Bitcoin was multifractal prior to the pandemic and becomes less fractal following the pandemic. They imply that Bitcoin is shown to be more efficient after the pandemic using an efficiency index (MLM). The authors demonstrated that this pandemic had lessened herd bias based on the Hausdorff topology.

Similarly, El Montasser, Charfeddine, and Benhamed (2022) compares the effectiveness of the bitcoin market before and after the Covid-19 pandemic to market bubble and non-bubble times. Additionally, it analyzes and groups 18 cryptocurrencies by considering how comparable their market efficiencies are. Their estimations show that the Covid-19 outbreak has the most significant influence on the efficiency of the bitcoin market when compared to periods of the cryptocurrency bubble. Also, they discovered evidence of the existence of three groups using the dynamic time-warping clustering approach, which effectively reflects mining coins, non-mining coins, and token categorizations.

To see some other aspects of this issue, Naeem et al. (2022) investigate the spillover properties of seven cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, Ethereum, Ripple, Litecoin, Monero, Stellar, and NEM) and by using VAR and quantile VAR models, they show that the three most important transmitters of return spillover are Bitcoin, Litecoin, and Ripple. The pairs of Ripple and Stellar have the strongest connections, followed by Bitcoin

and Litecoin. Interestingly, Ethereum is the system's constant recipient and is affected by the majority of cryptocurrencies. Additionally, NEM doesn't appear to be connected to any of the cryptocurrencies in the network that might operate as a possible diversifier.

According to finance literature, assets become more connected during an economic crisis. Covid-19, as an essential economic crisis, offers a chance to look into this phenomenon in more detail. To see if cryptocurrency futures are safe havens or diversifiers Goodell and Goutte (2021) investigates the impact of Covid-19 on the paired co-movements of six cryptocurrencies, including bitcoin futures, with fourteen equity indexes and the VIX (The Chicago Board Options Exchange's CBOE Volatility Index), and use several econometric techniques, including wavelet coherence, copula principal component, and neural network studies. They show as Covid-19 developed, co-movements between cryptocurrencies and equities indexes steadily grew. However, most of these co-movements are positive, indicating that cryptocurrencies do not offer the benefit of diversification during downturns. The co-movements of tether and bitcoin futures, which are negative with respect to stocks, are an exception. Their findings are consistent with investment vehicles that stand out as safe havens and draw in more knowledgeable or speculative investors.

Another interesting research Naeem et al. (2021) uses 1-hour data for Bitcoin, Ethereum, Litecoin, and Ripple to analyze the asymmetric efficiency of cryptocurrencies. They do this using the asymmetric multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis (MF-DFA). The price of cryptocurrencies shows significant asymmetric multifractality, with upward trends showing more multifractality than downward trends. They demonstrate that the Covid-19 pandemic had a negative impact on the four cryptocurrencies' efficiency using the time-varying deficiency metric, given a marked increase in inefficiency levels over the Covid-19 period. The two major cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin and Ethereum, were struck the hardest but also recovered more quickly from their abrupt decline into inefficiency at the end of March 2020. Their results support earlier evidence that market efficiency varies over time. Unprecedented catastrophic occurrences, like Covid-19, also have a negative impact on the performance of the top cryptocurrencies.

A different view on this issue is Kim and Lee (2021) that looks into how the cryptocurrency market's complexity has changed over time and examines its traits from the 2017 bull market to the Covid-19 pandemic. Three general complexity assessments based on nonlinear measures were employed to confirm the evolutionary complexity of the cryptocurrency market: approximate entropy (ApEn), sample entropy (SampEn), and Lempel-Ziv complexity (LZ). They examined the market's intricacy and volatility for 43 cryptocurrency values that have been trading up until recently. In order to cross-check quantitatively, three non-parametric tests appropriate for non-normal distribution comparison were used. Also, they examined the change in the complexity of the bitcoin market in response to events like Covid-19 and vaccination using the sliding time window methodology. The intricacy and unpredictability of the bitcoin market, from the bull market to the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak, have never been more clearly demonstrated than in this study. Due to various patterns, they discovered that the Covid-19 effect of complexity could not be generalized by ApEn, SampEn, and LZ complexity measures across all markets.

In the same vein, a country-specific research Jeribi and Manzli (2021) shows how Tunisia's crypto market performed throughout the Covid-19 outbreak. Using the OLS regression, they find that before the Covid-19 outbreak, Bitcoin served as a hedge, and Ethereum served as a diversifier for the Tunisian crypto market. However, during Covid-19, Bitcoin and Ethereum were unable to benefit financial investors through portfolio diversification and hedging strategies. Furthermore, they show that Dash, Monero, and Ripple serve as diversifiers and hedges during the Covid-19 pandemic. According to their findings, gold serves as a hedge and diversifier before the pandemic, but neither serves as a hedge nor a safe haven during the Covid-19 pandemic. Additionally, their findings showed that the anticipated volatility of the US stock market impacts the Tunisian crypto market. Also, the growing rate of Covid-19 confirmed cases and deaths appears to be detrimental to Tunisia's crypto market, according to their estimation.

Also, Banerjee et al. (2022) investigates how several Covid-19 news sentiment categories differently affect the behavior of bitcoin returns. To understand the dynamics of cryptocurrency, return, and volatility, a nonlinear transfer entropy technique is used in their study to look at the relationship between the top 30 cryptocurrencies by market capitalization and Covid-19 news sentiment. Their results indicate that the emotion of Covid-19 news affects cryptocurrency returns. They argue that, in contrast to earlier research, the link between news sentiment and bitcoin returns is one-way.

Using a different method, Fernandes et al. (2022) looks at the price disorder and informative effectiveness of five cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, BNB, Cardano, Ethereum, and XRP) before and during the Covid-19 outbreak. They calculate the Fisher information measure and permutation entropy (FIM). The Shannon-Fisher causality plane (SFPC), which maps these cryptocurrencies and their locations in a two-dimensional plane, is constructed using these complexity measurements. The sliding time window approach is then used to examine the temporal evolution of informational efficiency. During both times, all cryptocurrencies show high but slightly different informational efficiency. The most effective cryptocurrency was Cardano. These findings may indicate that cryptocurrencies are becoming more mature and have less possibility for price prediction, both of which are important for a strategy to diversify liquidity risk.

Finally, Wu, Wu, and Chen (2022) concentrates on how Covid-19 affects Bitcoin's high performance and long memory. They use a sliding window and the estimation of the Hurst exponent to get consistent, continuous time-varying results for Covid-19. The other four markets—Ethereum, Binance Coin, S&P 500, and gold spot—are also examined for comparison. According to Bitcoin results, the market remained efficient during the pandemic, and the hefty tails weakened after it started. According to the comparison study's findings, Bitcoin is more effective than Ethereum, Binance Coin, and S&P 500 during a pandemic and has an efficiency that is comparable to spot gold.

VOLATILITY OF CRYPTO MARKETS DURING COVID

Since the Covid-19 outbreak started, there has been an increase in the volatility of cryptocurrency markets. The pandemic has increased market instability and economic instability worldwide, and cryptocurrency markets are no exception. The fact that cryptocurrency markets are still relatively new and underdeveloped is a significant factor in their volatility. The cryptocurrency market is still in its early stages, in contrast to the stock market, which has a long history and is tightly regulated. The market is more volatile due to history and a lack of control. The decentralized nature of crypto markets is another element that makes them volatile. Since no single entity is in charge of the market, price swings can be more unstable.

In this area of research, Yousaf and Ali (2020) examines return and volatility transmission among Bitcoin, Ethereum, and Litecoin during the pre-Covid-19 and Covid-19 periods using intraday data and the VAR-DCC-GARCH model. They discover that the return spillovers for the Bitcoin-Ethereum, Bitcoin-Litecoin, and Ethereum-Litecoin pairs vary between the two time periods. The pre-Covid-19 period saw minimal volatility transmission between cryptocurrencies. Additionally, they show that during the Covid-19 period, the volatility spillover is unidirectional from Bitcoin to Ethereum and bidirectional between Ethereum and Litecoin. Furthermore, during the Covid-19 period, there is little to no volatility transmission between Bitcoin and Litecoin. In comparison to the pre-Covid-19 time, the dynamic conditional correlations between all cryptocurrency pairs are stronger during the Covid-19 period. They offer fresh perspectives on information flow channels, which could help portfolio investors make better investing and trading decisions during and outside of times of crisis.

Also, Al-Shboul, Assaf, and Mokni (2022) explores the dynamic spillovers among the significant cryptocurrencies under various market situations. They look into how the dynamic connectivity is impacted

by the uncertainty of cryptocurrency policy (CCPO) and price (CCPR). They use the Quantile-VAR technique to capture the left and right tails of the distributions corresponding to return spillovers under various market situations. They show that, in general, cryptocurrencies react to Covid-19 in a variety of ways. They discover that the Covid-19 pandemic has a noticeable effect on the total spillover index (TCI), which fluctuates across quantiles and climbs significantly during extreme market conditions. Litecoin overtook Bitcoin as the most critical "hedger" and/or "safe-haven" asset before and during the pandemic. During the covid crisis, Bitcoin lost its status as the primary "hedger." Their result also reveals that market uncertainty considerably impacts the five cryptocurrencies' overall net connectedness. They contend that the Covid-19 pandemic crisis significantly impacts how CCPO and CCPR are related dynamically across all market situations.

Similarly, Ftiti, Louhichi, and Ben Ameer (2021) investigates the problem of high-frequency data-based bitcoin volatility modeling and forecasting. They examine whether crises, notably the coronavirus pandemic, have an impact on the dynamics of bitcoin volatility. They examine the four major cryptocurrencies from April 2018 through June 2020 (Bitcoin, Ethereum Classic, Ethereum, and Ripple). Realized volatility is calculated and divided into some components (continuous versus discontinuous, positive and negative semi-variances, and signed jumps). These elements are included in a range of heterogeneous autoregressive (HAR) models, allowing for the examination of various modeling and volatility forecasting assumptions, including persistence and asymmetric dynamic, based on in-sample and out-of-sample forecasting methodologies, respectively. Their findings have three key conclusions. First, it seems that the extended HAR model, which considers both positive and negative jumps, is the most accurate at predicting future volatility, both during times of crisis and during times when there aren't any. Second, only the negative leap component is statistically significant during the crisis. Third, the results demonstrate that the extended HAR model incorporating positive and negative semi-variances outperforms the other models in forecasting volatility.

Furthermore, to see how the Covid-19 pandemic has affected the return-volatility and return-volume correlations, the ten most popular cryptocurrencies, Tether, Bitcoin, Ethereum, Ripple, Litecoin, Bitcoin Cash, EOS, Chainlink, Cardano, and Monero, are studied in Foroutan and Lahmiri (2022). In this study, the performance of cryptocurrencies during Covid-19 is also contrasted with that of less volatile markets like gold, WTI, and the Brent crude oil market. EGARCH-M model is used to research how volatility affects cryptocurrency return, while the VAR model and Granger causality tests are used to study return-volume correlations. Their findings demonstrate that during the Covid-19 pandemic, the return-volatility correlations for Tether, Ethereum, Ripple, Bitcoin Cash, EOS, and Monero are significant, whereas the exact relationship is not significant for any of the investigated cryptocurrencies before the pandemic. Their research on the return-volume relationship confirms the existence of causal links connecting returns to changes in trading volume for Chainlink and Monero prior to Covid-19 and for Ethereum, Ripple, Litecoin, EOS, and Cardano subsequent to Covid-19. However, when they looked at the absolute levels of returns, they discovered a substantial correlation between changes in trading volume for both the previous and Covid-19 periods and the absolute returns of cryptocurrencies. From a managerial standpoint, gold can be viewed as an appropriate asset for portfolio hedging during the pandemic, and trading volume can assist traders and investors in determining the impact of momentum and prospective trends in cryptocurrencies on their investments.

Finally, Corbet et al. (2022) looks at the relationships between cryptocurrency price volatility and liquidity during the Covid-19 pandemic. They suggest that during instances of significant financial market panic, these evolving digital assets may have taken on a new role as a potential safe haven. According to their findings, the liquidity of the cryptocurrency market dramatically surged after the WHO declared a global pandemic. The effects of bitcoin price and liquidity are found to interplay significantly. These findings lend more credence to the idea that significant volumes of investment sought refuge in the markets for cryptocurrencies during this rare black swan event.

RELATIONSHIPS WITH OTHER FINANCIAL ASSETS DURING COVID

Many consider cryptocurrencies a substitute for other assets like stocks, commodities, and fiat money. While there are some similarities between crypto assets and various other asset types, there are also significant differences. For instance, the price of cryptocurrencies is not always associated with the price of other assets, and they are frequently more volatile than other assets. So, investigating cryptocurrencies' relation with other assets during crises like Covid has significant implications for investors and traders.

One of the early papers is Vukovic et al. (2021) which looks into whether the cryptocurrency market is a safe haven for investors. According to them, gold, and oil, as typical global commodities, could have acted as diversifiers during the initial wave of the Covid-19 crisis. They created a particular Covid-19 global composite index that measures the pandemic's daily time-variant movements. The OLS, quantile, and robust regressions were employed in their study to examine whether the Covid-19 crisis had any significant direct effects on the cryptocurrency market. According to the OLS, quantile, and robust regression estimations, the Covid-19 problem had no statistically significant direct impact on the crypto market in the first wave period. Tether is an exception, but this study discovered spillovers from risky assets (S&P 500) on the cryptocurrency market. They argue that Tether may offer a safe haven in the crypto market because of the unique quality of a stablecoin.

Also, Jareño et al. (2021) examines, using a NARDL (nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag) methodology, the asymmetric interdependencies between the twelve major cryptocurrencies and Gold returns from January 2015 to June 2020. From March 2020 to June 2020, the Covid-19 pandemic's first wave is the subject of their investigation. They show that during this period of economic turbulence, the returns of various cryptocurrencies are becoming increasingly connected, and a growing number of cryptocurrencies have returns that are cointegrated with the returns of gold. Moreover, they show that throughout the Covid-19 period, cryptocurrency returns develop both a long-term and a short-term asymmetric reaction to the returns of gold. During this time, the majority of cryptocurrency returns respond more to negative changes and exhibit higher persistence with gold returns. Overall, the most important thing that they discovered is that in times of economic crisis, such as during the Covid-19 outbreak, there is an increase in the connectedness between the price of gold and the price of cryptocurrencies.

Similarly, Jalan, Matkovskyy, and Yarovaya (2021) compares five gold-backed stablecoins against gold, bitcoin, and Tether while experimentally analyzing their performance during the Covid-19 pandemic. They discovered that gold-backed cryptocurrencies were susceptible to volatility communicated from gold markets during the Covid-19 pandemic. Their findings show that the volatility of the chosen gold-backed cryptocurrencies, and consequently the dangers related to volatility, remained similar to those of Bitcoin. Additionally, gold-backed cryptocurrencies did not have the same safe-haven potential as the gold that served as their base metal.

Also, Wasiuzzaman and Rahman (2021) aims to look into how gold-backed cryptocurrencies performed during the Covid-19 crisis and, more specifically, during the bear market of 2020. The ARMA-GARCH model is used in their study to analyze the daily returns of PAX Gold from October 2, 2019, to September 28, 2020. The outcomes are contrasted with those of Gold and Paxos Standard (PAX) over the same time frame. Their findings indicate that during times of crisis, the three financial instruments' mean returns increase, though the increase is negligible. Insignificantly more volatility is experienced by PAX Gold during the Covid-19 crisis and the bear market.

Similarly, in a nonlinear and asymmetric framework using Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) methodology, Jeribi, Jena, and Lahiani (2021) examines the safe haven characteristics and

sustainability of the top five cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, Ethereum, Dash, Monero, and Ripple) and gold for the BRICS stock markets during the Covid-19 crisis period from January 31, 2020, to September 17, 2020, in comparison to the pre-crisis period from January 1, 2016, to January 30, 2020. Their findings demonstrate that throughout the Covid-19 crisis period, the relationship dynamics between the stock market and cryptocurrency returns are altering both in the short and long runs, which supports their use of a nonlinear and asymmetric model. Dash and Ripple are discovered to be a sustainable safe haven for all five marketplaces before the pandemic in terms of this concept. However, it has been discovered that all five cryptocurrencies served as a safe haven during the financial crisis for three emerging markets, including Brazil, China, and Russia. Only Brazil and Russia are found to be suitable safe havens for gold in a comparative context.

Using the recently created time-varying parameter vector autoregressive (TVP-VAR) based extended joint connectedness approach, Apergis, Chatziantoniou, and Gabauer (2022) examines the dynamic transmission mechanism between Covid-19 news sentiment (Google Trends Index), S&P100, crude oil, and gold volatility indexes proposed by Balcilar, Ozdemir, and Ozdemir (2021). Their empirical findings imply that Covid-19 has a significant negative impact on dynamic total connectedness and that it is heterogeneous across time. Moreover, they show that the Covid-19 news sentiment is the primary cause of spillover shocks, demonstrating that it is a significant predictor of the volatility indices used in the study. Thus, their findings have significant ramifications for decision-makers in the public and private sectors and portfolio and risk managers.

Also, using the VAR-BEKK-AGARCH model on hourly data, Yousaf and Ali (2021) investigates the return and volatility spillovers between the S&P 500 and cryptocurrencies (Litecoin (LTC), Bitcoin (BTC), and Ethereum (ETH)) during the pre-Covid-19 period and Covid-19 period. According to the study's findings, there were no appreciable returns or volatility spillovers between the US stock market and the cryptocurrency market before Covid-19. However, their analysis discovers that throughout the Covid-19 period, S&P 500 had a unidirectional return transmission to all cryptocurrencies. The volatility transmissions between the S&P 500 and Litecoin during the Covid-19 period are unidirectional, but they are insignificant for the pairs between the S&P 500 and Bitcoin and Ethereum.

In the same area of research, Le, Yarovaya, and Nasir (2021) investigates the impact of financial technology (Fintech) equities on other financial assets (such as gold, bitcoin, a global equity index, crude oil, and the US dollar) during the Covid-19 crisis. Their empirical research, which makes use of daily data from June 2019 to August 2020, reveals that the Covid-19 outbreak increased the spread of volatility across asset classes, whereas subsequent declines in new confirmed cases internationally decreased the strength of these spillovers. In contrast to innovative technology goods like Bitcoin and the financial technology index (KFTX), which are represented by the evidence, the USD and gold are safe haven assets during catastrophic situations. These findings demonstrate that the USD and gold are the ultimate arbiters of value when things go tough and that the USD's extravagant privileges allowed it to rule throughout the Covid-19 outbreak.

Also, Melki and Nefzi (2022) looks at how well three well-known cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, Ripple, and Ethereum) hedge and act as safe havens against the stock, commodities, and foreign exchange markets. Their findings, which were based on a logistic smooth transition regression model (LSTR2), show that monitored cryptocurrencies can function as safe-haven assets but that this behavior varies among different marketplaces. It's interesting to note that Ethereum has served as the commodity market's strongest safe haven throughout the pandemic. Their result has led to the conclusion that the Covid-19 outbreak offers a unique chance to learn more about the significance of emerging cryptocurrencies like Ethereum, which are edging out more established ones like Bitcoin in the cryptocurrency market.

Likewise, Khelifa, Guesmi, and Urom (2021) looked into the connection between hedge funds and the

bitcoin market through two different approaches. Using VAR and VECM models, they concentrate on the interdependence between cryptocurrency hedge funds and traditional hedge fund strategies while examining the effect of Covid-19 on the values of the hedge funds. Second, they compare the effects of cryptocurrency price movements on the valuations of cryptocurrency hedge funds during the Covid-19 crisis using the ARDL and ARDL-ECM models. Their empirical results show that there are significant interactions between traditional hedge funds and cryptocurrencies. Event Driven, Relative Value, and Distressed Debt fund strategies have all seen considerable declines in value during this crucial time due to the Covid-19 pandemic's significant negative impact on their performance. However, they show that the Covid-19 outbreak did not impact how cryptocurrency hedge funds interacted with bitcoin and Ethereum.

Finally, the relationship between oil price shocks and the top cryptocurrency returns is investigated in Jareño et al. (2021). This study also divides variations in crude oil prices into three important factors: risk, demand, and supply shocks. The first wave of the Covid-19 pandemic is studied in this research by using the NARDL methodology to investigate the relationship between oil and cryptocurrency between November 20, 2018, and June 30, 2020. Their findings support the notion that demand shocks correlate strongly with the returns of the examined cryptocurrencies. Additionally, both short-term and long-term findings indicate that oil and cryptocurrency are more interdependent during times of economic crisis, such as the coronavirus outbreak.

A PATH FORWARD

The impact of the pandemic on the global economy and financial system will likely define the crypto market's future in the post-COVID era. The pandemic has expedited the move to digital payments and online transactions, which is projected to increase crypto acceptance in the long run. Furthermore, the pandemic has underlined the significance of decentralized systems, which are a significant component of the cryptocurrency industry. This rising demand for digital assets and decentralized financial projects is expected to continue post-COVID.

The post-COVID future is also expected to witness institutional investors' widespread use of crypto assets. Traditional financial institutions have grown increasingly unstable due to the pandemic, which has increased the demand for decentralized alternatives. As more institutional investors seek crypto assets as a hedge against economic instability, this trend is anticipated to continue. In addition, the crypto market's enhanced regulatory clarity and institutional infrastructure are predicted to attract more institutional investors.

Consequently, it is predicted that the cryptocurrency market will expand further in the post-COVID period. The pandemic has increased the value of decentralized networks and pushed the transition to digital payment methods and online transactions. The widespread acceptance of crypto assets by institutional investors and the rising demand for digital assets and decentralized finance initiatives are both expected to persist.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

The goal of this study was to examine the rapidly growing body of research on the impact of Covid-19 on the crypto market and cryptocurrencies. Having used a systematic literature review method, studies published between February 2019 and January 2023 are considered in this paper.

The research in this area is organized into five major groups. First, the general state of the crypto market during the covid outbreak; second, the herding behavior of traders and investors during the covid outbreak; third, the impact of covid on cryptocurrency returns; fourth, the volatility of crypto markets during the covid outbreak; and finally, the relationship with other financial assets during the covid outbreak.

It seems that there is no comprehensive conclusion about the relationship between Covid and cryptocurrencies' performance. The findings vary depending on the model selection and model specification, sample collection, and research period. However, we cannot ignore the importance of digital assets such as cryptocurrencies in the future, and policymakers worldwide should pay more attention to the regulatory framework of the crypto market.

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